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Semantic Theories, Levels of meanings, and Types of meaning

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1- Theories of meaning

Breaking the circle in linguistics refers to the problem of defining meaning without using other words that have meaning. For example, if we define "meaning" as "the sense or import of something," then we have simply used the word "sense" to explain the word "meaning," which is not very helpful.

Also, imagine that you are trying to explain to a child what a *pen* is. You could start by saying that it is a long, thin object that you use to write. But the child might then ask you what *writing* is. And you might then have to explain that writing is a way of using symbols to represent language. But then the child might ask you what *language* is. This is the problem of the **definitional circle**. It is difficult to define one thing without using other words that also need to be defined. (Riemer, N. 2010)

1-1- Meanings as referents/denotations

There are a number of different theories try **to break the definitional circle**, and each theory has its own strengths and weaknesses. One theory is to define meaning in terms of **reference (referents/denotations)**. This means that the meaning of a word is the thing that the word refers to.

‘In its simplest form this theory would claim that reference picks out elements in the real world. As described by *Ruth Kempson* (1977: 13) such an approach might claim the following:

proper names	<i>denote</i>	individuals
common names	<i>denote</i>	sets of individuals
verbs	<i>denote</i>	actions
adjectives	<i>denote</i>	properties of individuals
adverbs	<i>denote</i>	properties of actions

(Saeed, 2016)

Another example: ‘*In Sydney, ‘the bridge’ means the Harbour Bridge*’. The speaker of this sentence is identifying the meaning of the word "bridge" with its referent, which is the *Sydney Harbour Bridge*. In other words, the speaker is saying that the word "bridge" means the same thing as the Sydney Harbour Bridge.

Problems with the referential theory of meaning:

- **Multiple referents:** A single referent can often be referred to by a variety of different expressions.
- **Abstract nouns / nominal expressions:** It is not clear what the referents of abstract nouns like "love, honor, pleasure, or generosity," or nominal expressions (World War III, a unicorn, might be. Since there is no isolable object in the world to which these nouns apply, the notion of a referent is rather hard to invoke or applied.
- **Grammatical words:** What are the denotations of grammatical words like "of" or "the"? These cases all pose problems for the referential theory of meaning: because the words have no referents/denotations, they are left without any specifiable meaning.

So, that means, **the referential theory of meaning** is unable to account for the full range of meanings that linguistic expressions can have. It is therefore necessary to look for a more sophisticated theory of meaning that can account for both the referential and non-referential aspects of meaning.

1-2- Meanings as concepts/mental representations

Another theory is to define meaning in terms of **concepts/ mental representations**. This means that the meaning of a word is the concept that the word represents in our minds. The concept theory of meaning identifies the meaning of a linguistic expression with the concept that it represents. Concepts are the basic constituents of thought, and they are what allow us to make sense of the world around us.

The concept theory of meaning has several advantages over the referential theory of meaning. **First**, it can account for the meaning of abstract nouns, which do not have referents in the real world. **Second**, it can account for the multiple referents of a single linguistic expression. **Third**, it can account for the meaning of grammatical words, which do not have denotations.

Example: ‘*Oliver is tolerant*’

The concept theory of meaning can explain why we understand the meaning of the sentence "*Oliver is tolerant*" even though the word "tolerant" has no single referent in the real world. The concept TOLERANCE is a complex concept that includes properties such as *patience, kindness, and respect for the opinions of others*. When we say "Oliver is tolerant," we are attributing these properties to Oliver.

The concept theory of meaning is a more sophisticated theory of meaning than the referential theory of meaning. It can account for the full range of meanings that linguistic expressions can have.

1- 3- Meanings as brain states

The brain states theory of meaning is a theory of meaning that holds that the meaning of a word or sentence is determined by the mental state that it expresses or evokes in the speaker or hearer. In other words, the meaning of a word or sentence is not determined by what it refers to or how it is used in language, but by the mental state that it is associated with. For example, the word "happy" is associated with the mental state of happiness, and the sentence "I am happy" evokes the mental state of happiness in the hearer. That means, the meaning of something is what it does to our brains. When we hear or read a word or sentence, our brains activate in certain ways. These brain activations are the meaning of the word or sentence.

- Example: When we hear the word "chair," our brains activate in a certain way. This brain activation is the meaning of the word "chair."

1- 4- Meaning and use

The use theory of meaning says that the meaning of a word is determined by how it is used. In other words, the meaning of a word is not something hidden or unobservable, but rather is something that can be seen in the way that the word is used in different contexts.

For example, the word "sorry" can be used to apologize for something you did wrong, or it can be used to express sympathy for someone who has experienced a loss. The meaning of the word "sorry" in each of these contexts is different, but the use theory of meaning says that both of these meanings are real, because they are both ways in which the word "sorry" is used.

The use theory of meaning is a simple and straightforward theory, and it is able to account for a wide range of phenomena related to language and meaning. However, it has been criticized for being too simplistic and for failing to account for certain aspects of meaning, such as the meaning of abstract concepts and the meaning of sentences that are not used in a literal way.

- Why do people believe in the use theory of meaning?

First, reason why people believe in the use theory of meaning is because it is a very simple and straightforward theory. It does not require us to believe in any hidden or unobservable properties of words. Instead, it simply says that the meaning of a word is determined by how we use it in language.

Another reason why people believe in the use theory of meaning is because it is very good at explaining a wide range of linguistic phenomena. For example, it can explain why the same word can have different meanings in different contexts, and why it is possible to create new meanings for words simply by using them in new ways.

2- Levels of meaning

Semantics is the study of the meaning of words and sentences. (Löbner S. 2013)

1- Expression meaning the meaning of a simple or complex expression taken in isolation. (ibid)

The example sentence "*I don't need your bicycle*" is a good illustration of semantics. The sentence has a literal meaning, which is that the speaker does not need the addressee's bicycle. However, the sentence can also have a variety of other meanings, depending on the context in which it is used.

The words *need* and *bicycle* are the main carriers of information in the sentence, so-called **content words**. The meanings of most content words are very differentiated because there are thousands of the same kind. All the other elements in our sentence are different in that they represent items from a very limited choice of expressions of the same kind. Such words are called **function words** and include articles, pronouns, prepositions, conjunctions and other 'small' words.

To understand the full meaning of the sentence, we need to consider a number of factors, including:

- **The meaning of the individual words:** The words "I," "don't," "need," "your," and "bicycle" all have their own individual meanings.
- **The grammatical structure of the sentence:** The way that the words are arranged in the sentence also affects its meaning. For example, the fact that the subject of the sentence is "I" tells us that the speaker is the one who does not need the bicycle.
- **The context in which the sentence is used:** The context in which the sentence is used can also affect its meaning. For example, if the speaker and addressee are friends, the sentence might be interpreted as a playful joke. However, if the speaker and addressee are strangers, the sentence might be interpreted as a rude refusal.

2- Utterance meaning the meaning of an expression when used in a given context of utterance resulting from fixing reference. Utterance meaning is the meaning of a sentence when it is actually used in a concrete context. It is different from the lexical meaning of a sentence, which is the meaning of a sentence independently of its context. (Ibid)

- Sentence meaning, utterance meaning

Sentence meaning is the meaning of a sentence in isolation, regardless of the context in which it is used. It is the meaning that can be derived from the words and grammar of the sentence alone. With sentence meaning we refer to semantics.

Utterance meaning is the meaning of utterance when it is used in a specific context. It is the meaning (sense) that is intended by the speaker or writer, taking into account the context in which the sentence is used. With utterance meaning we refer to Pragmatics.

SCENARIO 1	SCENARIO 2
1 August 2012, morning. Mary has been planning a trip to town that afternoon. Two days before, she talked with her neighbour John about the trip and asked him to lend her his bicycle. She had lent her car to her daughter and did not know if she would get it back in time. Meanwhile her daughter is back and has returned Mary's car. Mary is talking with John on her mobile, telling him: <i>I don't need your bicycle.</i>	Same time and place. John's five-year-old daughter Maggie is playing at her place with her friend Titus. They are playing with a game of cards that display all kinds of vehicles. Titus holds a card that shows a snowmobile. Maggie is eager to exchange this card for one of hers and offers Titus a card with a bicycle. Titus rejects the exchange: <i>I don't need your bicycle.</i>

The sentence above "***I don't need your bicycle***" has the same lexical meaning in the two scenarios given in the example. However, its utterance meaning is different in each scenario.

In the first scenario, the speaker is telling her neighbor that she does not need to borrow his bicycle because she has her car back.

In the second scenario, the speaker is telling her friend's child that she does not want to trade her card for his card because she prefers to keep her bicycle card.

The context of utterance includes all of the information that is relevant to understanding the meaning of an utterance, such as the speaker, the listener, the time and place of the utterance, and the shared knowledge of the speaker and listener. The technical term for this is **context of utterance**. The context of utterance, **CoU** for short, is the sum of circumstances that. The context of utterance (CoU) comprises the following aspects of the situation in which an utterance is produced:

- ❖ the **speaker** (or producer) of the utterance
- ❖ the **addressee(s)** (or recipient(s)) of the utterance
- ❖ the **time** at which the utterance is produced and/or received
- ❖ the **place** where the utterance is produced and/or received
- ❖ the **facts** given when the utterance is produced and/or received

The notion of utterance meaning is important because it allows us to understand how language is used in communication. When we understand the utterance meaning of a sentence, we can understand what the speaker is trying to communicate, even if the sentence is ambiguous or has multiple possible interpretations. Utterance meaning is a complex topic, but it is an important one to understand in order to understand how language is used in communication.

3- Communicative meaning the meaning of an utterance as a communicative act in a given social setting. (Ibid) Communicative meaning is the level of interpretation of an utterance that is concerned with the speaker's intention. It is the meaning that the speaker wants to convey to the listener, and it is determined by the context of the utterance, including the speaker-listener relationship and the ongoing social interaction.

The three levels of meaning are:

- **Expression meaning:** The meaning of the individual words and sentences that make up the utterance.
- **Utterance meaning:** The meaning of the utterance as a whole, taking into account the context of the utterance, such as the speaker-listener relationship and the ongoing social interaction.
- **Communicative meaning:** The speaker's intention in uttering the sentence.

3- Seven Types of Meaning

1-Conceptual meaning (sometimes called '*denotative*' or '*cognitive*' meaning). This is the core meaning of a word or phrase, and it is what is typically found in dictionaries. For example, the conceptual meaning of the word "dog" is a four-legged, furry mammal that barks. So, it is the literal meaning of word.

2- Connotative Meaning: Connotative meaning is the communicative value that an expression has by virtue of what it refers to. Connotative meaning is the communicative value that an expression has by virtue of what it refers to, It is the 'real world' experience that one associates with an expression when one uses or hears it. Connotative meaning is peripheral to conceptual meaning because it is relatively unstable, indeterminate and open-ended. It varies according to culture, historical period, and the experience of the individual. In contrast, conceptual meaning is generally taken as fundamental to semantic theory and is assumed to be finite and determinate. In other words, it is the additional meaning that a word or phrase has beyond its conceptual meaning. It can include associations, emotions, and cultural references. For example, the connotative meaning of the word "dog" might include loyalty, friendship, and playfulness.

3- **Social meaning:** is that which a piece of language conveys about the social circumstances of its use. It is conveyed through different dimensions and levels of style within the same language, such as dialect, time, province, status, modality, and singularity.

In a more local sense, social meaning can include what has been called the *illocutionary force* of an utterance. For example, whether it is to be interpreted as a request, an assertion, an apology, a threat, etc. The function an utterance performs in this respect may be only indirectly related to its conceptual meaning. The sentence *I haven't got a knife* has the form and meaning of an assertion, and yet in social reality (e.g. if said to the waiter in a restaurant) it can readily take on the force of a request such as *'Please bring me a knife'*.

4- **Affective meaning** is the personal feelings of the speaker, including his attitude to the listener, or his attitude to something he is talking about. It is often explicitly conveyed through the conceptual or connotative content of the words used, but can also be conveyed through politeness, intonation, and voice-timbre.

Affective meaning is largely a parasitic category in the sense that to express our emotions we rely upon the mediation of other categories of meaning- conceptual, connotative, or stylistic. Emotional expression through style comes about, for instance, when we adopt an impolite tone to express displeasure, as in this example (*Will you belt up.*), or when we adopt a casual tone to express friendliness. On the other hand, there are elements of language (like *Aha!* and *yippee!*) whose chief function is to express emotion. When we use these, we communicate feelings and attitudes without the mediation of any other kind of semantic function. We can say, it is the emotional meaning of a word or phrase. For example, the word *"happy"* has a positive affective meaning, while the word *"sad"* has a negative affective meaning.

- *Affective meaning:*
 - "Oh my goodness!" (surprise)
 - "I'm so happy for you!" (joy)
 - "You're a terrible person!" (anger)

5- **Reflected meaning:** is the meaning which arises in cases of multiple conceptual meaning, when one sense of a word forms part of our response to another sense. Reflected meaning, which is a phenomenon whereby a single word or phrase is associated with more than one sense or meaning. In the example Leech gives, the words *"The Comforter"* and *"The Holy Ghost"* both refer to the Third Person of the Trinity, but they have different everyday meanings. The word *"comforter"* is associated with warmth and comfort, while the word *"ghost"* is associated with awe and fear. In other words, reflected meaning: This is the meaning that a word or phrase has because of its relationship to other words or phrases in the text. For example, the word *"red"* in the sentence *"The red rose is beautiful"* has a different reflected meaning than the word *"red"* in the sentence *"The red traffic light is on."*

6- **Collocative meaning**; consists of the associations a word acquires on account of the meanings of words which tend to occur in its environment. *Pretty* and *handsome* share common ground in the meaning 'good-looking', but may be distinguished by the range of nouns with which they are likely to co-occur or collocate (*Pretty girl, boy, woman, flower, colour, etc.*).

Here are some examples of collocative meaning:

- The words "hot" and "cold" are often collocated with drinks, such as "hot coffee" and "cold water."
- The words "big" and "small" are often collocated with objects, such as "big house" and "small car."

7- **Thematic meaning**, or what is communicated by the way in which a speaker or writer organizes the message, in terms of ordering, focus, and emphasis. It is often felt, for example, that an active sentence such as (Mr. Smith donated the first prize.) has a different meaning from its passive equivalent (The first prize was donated by Mr. Smith.), although in conceptual content they seem to be the same. Certainly, these have different communicative values in that they suggest different contexts.

Thematic meaning is mainly a matter of choice between alternative **grammatical construction**, as in:

- A man is waiting in the hall.
- There's a man waiting in the hall.

In other cases, it is **stress and intonation** rather than grammatical construction that highlights information in one part of a sentence. If the word *electric* is given contrastive stress in: (Bill uses an **electric** razor.) The effect is to focus attention on that word as containing new information, against a background of what is already assumed to be known.

4- Associative Meaning:

Reflected meaning, collocative meaning, affective meaning and social meaning: all these have more in common with *connotative meaning* than with *conceptual meaning*; they all have the same open-ended, variable character, and lend themselves to analysis in terms of scales or ranges, rather than in discrete either-this-or-that terms. They can all be brought together under the heading of associative meaning, and to explain communication on these levels. In other words, associative meaning is a type of meaning that is not based on the literal, or conceptual, meaning of words. It is instead based on the associations that we have with words, such as their emotional connotations, their social implications, and the way they are used in different contexts. (Leech, 1981)

Associative meaning is often more difficult to define and understand than conceptual meaning, but it is also more nuanced and expressive. It is an important part of how we

communicate with each other, and it is what gives language its richness and complexity. example of associative meaning:

- The word "home" has a different associative meaning for everyone. It may be associated with family, safety, comfort, or a sense of belonging.

Associative meaning is what allows us to understand and appreciate things like poetry, literature, and music. It is also what allows us to communicate with each other on a deeper level, beyond the literal meaning of words.

5- Demarcation Problems:

The difficulties of demarcating the boundaries between different types of meaning. For example, it can be difficult to distinguish between conceptual meaning and connotative meaning, or between conceptual meaning and socio-stylistic meaning.

Such as in the following examples:

- The difference between the sentences "*He stuck the key in his pocket*" and "*He put the key in his pocket*" could be seen as a matter of style, or it could be seen as a conceptual difference, with the word "stick" having a more precise denotation in the first sentence.
- The difference between the verbs "*smile*" and "*grin*" could be seen as a matter of collocation, or it could be seen as a conceptual difference, with a grin being a broader, toothier, and more potentially hostile expression than a smile.

SEVEN TYPES OF MEANING	1- Conceptual meaning or Sense		Logical, cognitive, or denotative content.
	ASSOCIATIVE MEANING	2.Connotative meaning	What is communicated by virtue of what language refers to.
		3.Social meaning	What is communicated of the social circumstances of language use.
		4. Affective meaning	What is communicated of the feelings and attitudes of the speaker/writer.
		5. Reflected meaning	What is communicated through association with another sense of the same expression.
		6. Collocative meaning	What is communicated through association with words which tend to occur in the environment of another word.
	7. Thematic meaning		What is communicated by the way in which the message is organized in terms of order and emphasis.

6- Conclusions

This paper offers a concise overview of prominent theories and levels of meaning in linguistics, highlighting the dynamic interplay between language and interpretation.

Breaking the Definitional Circle:

- Various theories tackle the challenge of defining meaning without circularity.
- Reference theories define meaning based on what words refer to, while concept theories focus on mental representations associated with words.
- Recent advancements explore meaning as emergent from brain states or contextual usage.

Levels of Meaning:

- **Expression meaning:** The literal, dictionary definition of a word or sentence.
- **Utterance meaning:** The context-dependent interpretation of an utterance, considering speaker, listener, and situation.
- **Communicative meaning:** The speaker's intended message, encompassing both literal and implicit communication.

Seven Types of Meaning:

1. **Conceptual meaning:** The core, denotative meaning of a word or phrase.
2. **Connotative meaning:** Additional associations, emotions, and cultural references evoked by a word.
3. **Social meaning:** The social context and implications associated with language use.
4. **Affective meaning:** The emotional tone and speaker's attitude conveyed through language.
5. **Reflected meaning:** The meaning arising from a word's relationship to other words in a text.
6. **Collocative meaning:** The association of a word with other words it typically co-occurs with.
7. **Thematic meaning:** The emphasis and information structure conveyed through the organization of a message.

Associative Meaning:

- A broader category encompassing connotative, collocative, affective, and social meaning.
- Beyond literal meaning, these associations contribute to the richness and nuance of language communication.

Demarcation Challenges:

- Distinguishing between different types of meaning can be complex due to their interconnectedness and fluidity.
- Recognizing these intricacies is crucial for a comprehensive understanding of how meaning is constructed and interpreted.

This paper provides a foundation for further exploration of the multifaceted nature of meaning in language. By examining the interplay between theories, levels, and types of meaning, the researcher gains a deeper appreciation for the human capacity to create and decipher complex communication.

Interrelationships between different theories of meaning: potential for integration or complementary views. Cultural and individual influences on language use and meaning interpretation.

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